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Review Article

EXOSOMES LOADED HYDROGEL IN SKIN REGENERATION¹ Miss P. Sony, ² Dr. K. Umasankar*, ³ Dr. K. Venugopal¹ Final year B. Pharmacy, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati-517506² Professor & Head of the Department (Department of Pharmaceutics), Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati-517506³ Professor & Principal Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati-517506**Abstract:**

Nanoscale lipid bilayer vesicles called exosomes have become a viable treatment option for skin regeneration. Exosomes, which are derived from mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs), are abundant in growth hormones and proteins that promote wound healing and tissue regeneration. Exosomes' therapeutic efficacy is increased by loading them onto hydrogels, which offers a regulated release mechanism. Hydrogels provide the perfect platform for exosome distribution because of their biocompatibility and adjustable mechanical characteristics. This method has demonstrated promise in supporting tissue repair, wound healing, and skin regeneration. It has been demonstrated that exosomes put onto hydrogels improve wound healing results by promoting cell migration, proliferation, and differentiation. They have also been shown to stimulate tissue remodelling, lower inflammation, and alter the immunological response. Exosomes have been utilized in cosmetics to lessen wrinkles, increase skin elasticity, improve skin texture and hydration, and lessen UV radiation-induced inflammation and damage. Because of their versatility, exosomes and hydrogels can be used for a variety of skin-related applications, such as tissue engineering, wound healing, and skin rejuvenation. Exosome infusion is one of these applications, and hydrogels have been shown to be the most accessible, affordable, and user-friendly material. In addition to outlining the main benefits, difficulties, and probable future approaches in this field, this paper highlights the potential of exosomes loaded on hydrogels as a therapeutic strategy for skin regeneration.

Key Words: Exosomes, Hydrogel, Wound healing, Biogenesis, Therapeutic applications.

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INTRODUCTION:

- A range of proteins and genetic material, including mRNA and miRNA, are found within exosomes, which are nanoscale lipid bilayer vesicles with a diameter of about 30-200 nm.
- Exosomes are produced when multivesicular bodies (MVBs) with intraluminal vesicles (ILV) bud inside of them. They are then released through the endosomal-lysosomal pathway and are progressively rising to prominence in intracellular communication related to a variety of physiological and pathological processes.
- A variety of biological functions are also carried out by them, such as immune system modulation, tissue repair, and cell-to-cell communication (1).
- The ability of exosomes to influence every stage of wound healing has been demonstrated in numerous researches.
- management of disorders and skin dysfunction.
- In regenerative medicine and aesthetics, stem cells and other cell types may be therapeutic

possibilities, particularly in the areas of hair growth, pigmentation modulation, and scar avoidance and reduction. For example, exosomes released by melanocytes can regulate skin pigmentation, and exosomes from other skin cell types can similarly influence melanocyte melanin production.

- According to the skin sensitization test, exosomes made from MSCs were likewise deemed to be potentially non-sensitizers and safe for topical application without causing any negative side effects. Exosomes have been shown to have potential use in medicine, cosmetics, and other biological fields.

History

Exosomes were first discovered in the maturing mammalian reticulocyte [immature red blood cells] by Stahl and group in 1983 and Johnstone and group in 1983 further termed exosomes by Johnstone and group in 1987.

Advantages

- Due to worries about instability and the possibility of malignancy, MSC-based tissue engineering techniques for clinical treatments have drawn attention.
- MSC-derived exosomes have gained attention as a possible substitute for conventional stem cell treatments. MSC-exos and MSCs perform comparable tasks in terms of immune control, tissue healing, and inflammation inhibition.

- They can circulate through capillaries, avoid immunity problems, and be kept for extended periods of time. Exosomes, however, are quickly removed from the blood and accumulate in the gastrointestinal tract, lung, spleen, and liver, among other organs.
- In order to increase local release and extend the plasma half-life of exosomes, implantable biomaterial scaffolds have been constructed. Exosomes loaded in hydrogels for skin regeneration offer several advantages:

- i. **Improved Delivery:** Hydrogels offer a framework that permits exosomes to be released continuously, guaranteeing that bioactive molecules remain in the target location for an extended period of time.
- ii. **Biocompatibility:** Hydrogels are frequently composed of biocompatible substances, which reduces the possibility of negative skin reactions.
- iii. **Cellular Communication:** Proteins, lipids, and RNAs found in exosomes help cells communicate with one another, which in turn promotes cell division and proliferation—two processes essential for skin regeneration.
- iv. **Anti-Inflammatory Properties:** A number of exosomes have anti-inflammatory qualities that can aid in lowering inflammation brought on by skin disorders or accidents.
- v. **Wound Healing Acceleration:** By encouraging collagen synthesis and angiogenesis, the development of new blood vessels, which are critical for tissue repair, exosomes can speed up the healing process.
- vi. **Customization:** Hydrogels can be designed to regulate exosome release rates, allowing for the customization of treatment to meet certain healing requirements.
- vii. **Decreased Scar Formation:** Exosomes' healing qualities can lessen scarring, improving cosmetic results.
- viii. **Hydrogels have the ability to retain moisture,** which promotes healing and enhances the general health of the skin.
- ix. **Minimally Invasive:** When compared to more conventional skin care or grafting techniques, this method may be less invasive.
- x. **Combination therapy potential:** Exosome-loaded hydrogels can be used in conjunction with other medicinal substances or therapies to increase their effectiveness in skin regeneration.

Because of these benefits, exosome-loaded hydrogels show promise as a means of enhancing skin regeneration and healing.

Disadvantages

- **Stability Problems:** Exosomes are environment-sensitive. When inserted into hydrogels, they could eventually lose their usefulness or experience structural alterations, particularly if the hydrogel matrix is not biocompatible.
- **Potential Immunogenicity:** There may be a chance of immunological reactions if the hydrogel or exosomes come from non-autologous sources. These reactions could cause inflammation or other negative effects.

- **Cost:** Exosome-loaded hydrogel development and production can be costly, which restricts its availability for clinical use.
- **Diffusion Limitations:** Exosomes may find it difficult to efficiently reach target cells or tissues due to the physical characteristics of the hydrogel that obstruct their diffusion.
- **Problems with Cellular Uptake:** The hydrogel matrix may prevent recipient cells from absorbing exosomes, which could lessen the therapeutic effect of the particles.

Types of Exosomes loaded on hydrogels for skin regeneration

- **Exosome types used into hydrogels to promote skin regeneration**
- **Exosomes Derived from Mesenchymal Stem Cells:** These exosomes are abundant in proteins and growth factors that facilitate tissue regeneration and wound repair. They can improve the migration and proliferation of skin cells when added to hydrogels.
- **Platelet-Derived Exosomes:** These exosomes are useful for quickening the healing of wounds since they are loaded into hydrogels and contain a variety of growth factors involved in tissue repair and haemostasis.
- **Exosomes Derived from Keratinocytes:** When added to hydrogels, keratinocyte-derived exosomes have the potential to improve epithelial regeneration and aid in the restoration of the skin barrier.
- **Adipose-Derived Stem Cell Exosomes:** These exosomes can stimulate angiogenesis, which is essential for skin regeneration, and they also have anti-inflammatory qualities. Their addition to hydrogels can aid in preserving moisture and accelerating the healing process.
- **Fibroblast exosomes:** These exosomes have the ability to enhance the extracellular matrix, which is necessary for the structure and suppleness of skin, and to promote the manufacture of collagen.
- **Synthetic Exosomes:** Scientists are also investigating exosomes that are engineered or synthetic and can be customized to transport particular medicinal substances. These chemicals can be released in a regulated manner into hydrogels to promote skin regeneration.
- **Natural Exosomes:** Researchers are looking into the healing qualities of exosomes obtained from a variety of natural sources, such as plants, and how they may be incorporated into hydrogels.

Suitable candidate

Every kind of exosome has distinct advantages, and combining them with hydrogels is meant to increase. Many individuals can benefit from exosomes put on hydrogels for skin regeneration, especially those with diseases that hinder skin healing or call for regenerative support. The following are a few possible candidate groups:

- **Individuals with Long-Term Injuries**
Diabetic Ulcers: Due to reduced immune response and poor circulation, people with diabetes frequently experience slow-healing ulcers.
Pressure Ulcers: People with restricted movement may have pressure sores, which call more sophisticated treatment techniques.
Venous Stasis Ulcers: Improved wound healing methods may be helpful for individuals suffering from venous insufficiency.
- **Burned Individuals**
Severe Burns: To encourage skin regeneration and reduce scarring, patients with partial or full-thickness burns may benefit from hydrogels filled with exosomes.
- **Patients After Surgery**
Surgical Incisions: People recuperating from surgery, particularly those with intricate or sizable incisions, can gain from quicker healing
- **Aging Population**
Age-Related Skin Degeneration: Advanced regenerative therapies can benefit older persons who often have slower wound healing and decreased skin suppleness.
- **Patients with Skin Diseases:**
Exosome therapy can be used to control immune responses and enhance healing in the treatment of psoriasis and eczema, two inflammatory skin disorders.
- **Trauma Patients**
Lacerations and Abrasions: Exosomes' healing qualities may be advantageous for people who have had severe skin injuries.
- **Cosmetic Applications**
Anti-Aging Treatments: Hydrogels filled with exosomes can be utilized in cosmetic operations to enhance the texture and encourage skin renewal.
- **People Affected by Autoimmune Diseases**
Skin disorders such as Scleroderma: In order to prevent tissue damage, patients with autoimmune skin conditions may need to employ improved healing techniques.
- **Skin Graft Recipients**
Improving Graft Survival: Exosome-loaded hydrogels may help patients having skin grafts

integrate their transplants better and experience fewer problems.

- **Immunocompromised Patients**
People with Compromised Immune Systems: These people may have trouble healing wounds, which makes them good candidates for exosome therapies, which can boost the immune system locally.

Applications**Disease Diagnosis**

- Exosomes serve as rich sources of biomarkers for disease diagnosis and prognosis, particularly in cancer, cardiovascular diseases, tuberculosis, and central nervous system diseases.
- Exosomal microRNAs such as miR-499, miR-133, miR-208, miR-192, miR-194, and miRNA-34a show potential as diagnostic markers for cardiovascular diseases.
- Exosomes can be used for diagnosing Dysferlinopathy by evaluating the absence of dysferlin in patients' exosomes.
- Different exosomal biomarkers, including miR-21, miR-29, miR-219, miR-199, LRP6, REST1, and caveolin1, demonstrate clinical diagnostic potential for central nervous system diseases.
- Tumour exosomes, abundant in biofluids, can aid in liquid biopsy for early tumour diagnosis by detecting specific biomarkers such as exosomal protein CD151, miR-1246, miR-21, and miR-638 associated with lung cancer, breast cancer, and colorectal cancer.
- Exosomal detection technology, exemplified by ExoDX Lung (ALK), shows promise in real-time screening for specific mutations in non-small cell lung cancer, aiding in targeted therapy decisions.

Disease Treatment Through Exosome-Targeted Drug Delivery System

- Exosomes are small in size, avoiding phagocytosis and freely crossing biological barriers.
- They have better biocompatibility and low immunogenicity compared to other delivery systems.
- Exosomes enter cells through various proteins on their surface, mainly via receptor-mediated endocytosis.
- They have the ability to target tissues, penetrate biological barriers, and transport contents efficiently.
- Natural exosomes may have weak targeting and be quickly cleared, leading to poor treatment effect.

- Engineered exosomes, loaded with therapeutic agents or modified, aim to address these issues. The targeted delivery system of exosomes will be explained from the perspectives of drug loading and surface modification.

Freeze-Drying Technology

- Freeze-drying involves cooling and freezing materials containing moisture, then sublimating the ice under vacuum to remove it as water vapor, meeting storage requirements.
- The process includes three stages: pre-freezing, sublimation drying, and analytical drying.
- Freeze-dried exosomal lyophilized powder reduces storage conditions, maintaining original activity and minimizing damage to biological tissues and cells.
- Suitable for preserving heat-sensitive materials such as EVs, vaccines, and proteins. - Antifreezes are selectively added to protect biological materials during freeze-drying.
- Addition of trehalose prevents exosome aggregation during freeze-drying, increases

colloidal stability, and does not change exosome morphology.

- Lyophilized exosomes stored at room temperature maintain protein content and have minimal effect on pharmacokinetics compared to those stored at -80°C.
- Spray drying is a technique used for drying materials through atomization and quick vaporization of moisture with hot air
- Factors affecting stability of exosomes during spray drying include atomization pressure and outlet temperature
- Spray drying is a continuous process and allows for one-step milling, making it more economical and adjustable in product particle size
- The best comprehensive storage method for exosomes is -80°C frozen storage
- Storage at -80°C for extended periods can affect the morphology and biological activity of exosomes
- Research is needed to study storage stability of exosomes from various perspectives to facilitate subsequent functional studies and expand their application scope.

Isolation methods of exosomes

Here are a few methods that are often employed:

1. **Ultrafiltration:** This technique divides exosomes from other cellular constituents according to size using membranes with predetermined pore diameters. It is effective and permits exosome concentration.
2. **Ultracentrifugation:** This age-old method divides exosomes according to density by rapidly rotating cell culture medium. Usually, there are several processes involved, such as differential centrifugation.
3. **Precipitation Methods:** Exosomes can be precipitated from the culture media using commercial kits that employ solutions based on polymers. Although this method is often faster and easier, its purity might be poorer.
4. **Affinity-based Methods:** These procedures separate exosomes using antibodies or other binding agents that are particular to exosomal surface marks. Although it can require specialized knowledge of exosomal markers, this technique can improve purity.
5. **Exclusion of size Chromatography (SEC):** As exosomes move through a column, this technique divides them into groups according to size. It offers a tactful method that maintains the integrity and functionality of exosomes.
6. **Microfluidic Techniques:** These are more recent techniques that separate exosomes from biological fluids using microfabricated devices. They are able to offer efficient separation at a high throughput.
7. **Bead-based Isolation:** This method makes use of magnetic beads that have been coated in antibodies that bind to exosomal markers. A

magnetic field can be used to collect the exosomes after they have been combined with the material.

Depending on the required release properties and stability, exosomes can be loaded into hydrogels utilizing a variety of techniques, including mixing during gel formation or post-gelation injection. Every isolation technique has benefits and drawbacks, thus the decision frequently

Characterization Methods

- **Techniques for Characterization**
- **Nanoparticle Tracking Analysis (NTA):** Purpose: Tracks exosome motion in solution to determine exosome concentration and size. Benefits: Offers analysis in real time.
- **Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM):** Summary: Provides a nanoscale visual of exosomes. Benefits: Offers thorough morphology.
- **Western Blotting:** Using antibodies, this method finds certain proteins in exosomes. Benefits: Helpful in verifying exosomal markers.
- **Flow Cytometry:** Definition: Examines exosome size and surface indicators. Benefits: Makes multi-parameter analysis possible.
- **Mass Spectrometry:** Describes: This technique locates and measures the lipids and proteins contained in exosomes. Benefits: Offers thorough molecular profiling. Taken together, these techniques provide the efficient separation and description of exosomes for a range of purposes, such as medical and diagnostic ones.

Formulation of exosomes loaded on hydrogels

preparation of hydrogel-loaded exosomes. To ensure efficient transport and activity, formulating exosomes placed on hydrogels for skin regeneration requires a number of critical steps. The following are a few typical formulation methods:

- 1) **Physical Blending:**
Before gelation, hydrogel precursors are combined with exosomes.
Procedure: To create the gel, the exosome solution is mixed with hydrogel constituents (such as polymers) and polymerized.
Benefits: Easy to understand and preserves exosome integrity.
- 2) **In Situ Gelation:** In situ gelation occurs when a solution changes in reaction to changes in pH or temperature. In this scenario, exosomes are added to the solution.
Procedure: After adding exosomes to a solution, it gels under specific circumstances.
Benefits: Reduces exosome exposure to abrasive environments during gel formation.
- 3) **Freeze-Drying (Lyophilization):** Described as follows: Exosomes are rehydrated in hydrogel solutions after being freeze-dried.
Procedure: Cryoprotectants are combined with exosomes, frozen, and then lyophilized. Subsequently, they are restored within the hydrogel composition.
Benefits: Makes storing simpler and increases stability.
- 4) **Electrospinning:** Synopsis: Hydrogel-based electrospun fibers can be combined with exosomes.
Procedure: An exosome-containing solution is electrospun into nanofibers to produce a scaffold that can be applied to the regrowth of skin.
Benefits: Offers a porous structure that improves nutrition exchange and cell infiltration.
- 5) **Assembly of Layers by Layers (LbL):** Exosomes and hydrogel materials are layered in alternate fashion.
Procedure: Layers of exosomes are deposited to provide controlled release and cell-to-cell contact.
Benefits: Offers exact control over the release profile and composition.
- 6) **Microencapsulation:** Synopsis: Prior to being combined with hydrogels, exosomes are encapsulated in microparticles or nanocarriers.
Procedure: Microparticles containing exosomes can be produced by methods such as solvent evaporation or spray drying, and they can then be added to hydrogels.

Benefits: Preserves exosomes and permits prolonged release.

- 7) **3D Biomanufacturing:**
Description: Incorporates exosomes into hydrogels using bioprinting processes.
Procedure: Bio-ink is combined with exosomes and printed into the desired shapes.
Benefits: Allows for exact spatial control of hydrogel architecture and exosome distribution.
- 8) **Injection Following Gelation:**
Exosomes are injected into hydrogels that have already been produced.
Procedure: To enable localized delivery, hydrogels are first produced, and then exosomes are injected.
Benefits: Reduces exposure to abrasive environments while hydrogel is forming.

Each strategy has benefits and drawbacks, and the formulation method used usually depends on the specific requirements for skin regeneration, such as stability, release kinetics, and tissue compatibility.

Evaluation methods

Evaluating exosomes loaded on hydrogels for skin regeneration involves several methods to assess their properties, efficacy, and biological interactions. Here are key evaluation methods:

- a. **Exosome Characterization:** Nanoparticle Tracking Analysis (NTA): Determines the exosome concentration and size distribution. Using transmission electron microscopy (TEM), exosome morphology can be seen. Verifies the existence of particular exosome markers (such as CD63 and CD81) using western blotting. Exosome stability and size are examined using dynamic light scattering (DLS) in suspension.
- b. **Characterization of Hydrogen:** Testing for Rheology: evaluates the hydrogel's mechanical characteristics, such as its elasticity and viscosity.
Swelling Ratio: Evaluates the hydrogel's capacity for fluid absorption.
Degradation Rate: Measures the hydrogel's rate of breakdown under physiological settings.
- c. **Exosome Loading Efficiency:** Centrifugation and Quantification: Quantifies the supernatant both before and after loading to ascertain how many exosomes were injected into the hydrogel.
Fluorescent Labelling: This technique makes use of fluorescent tags to measure and see how long exosomes stay inside the hydrogel.
- d. **Release Kinetics:** In Vitro Release Studies: Frequently employing a dialysis technique, this

study tracks the exosomes' release profile from the hydrogel over time. Quantifies the quantity of exosomes released into the surrounding media using ELISA or fluorescence assays.

- e. **Biocompatibility and Cytotoxicity: MTT or Alamar Blue Assays:** Determine the survival of skin cells exposed to the hydrogel and exosomes produced. Examples of these cells include fibroblasts and keratinocytes. **Live/Dead Staining:** Shows the viability of the cells following hydrogel and exosome treatment.
- f. **Research on Skin Regeneration: In vitro Scratch Assays:** assesses how well treated cells can migrate and multiply to replicate the healing of wounds. **Animal Models:** Examines tissue integration, skin regeneration, and wound healing utilizing animal models in in vivo research.
- g. **Molecular Analysis: Research on Gene Expression:** uses RT-qPCR to analyze the expression of important genes (such as growth factors and cytokines) involved in skin regeneration. **Protein Analysis:** Uses ELISA to quantify growth factors or cytokines secreted from treated cells.
- h. **Histological Analysis: Tissue Staining:** Assesses collagen deposition, cell infiltration, and tissue structure in skin that has undergone regeneration using histological techniques. **Immunofluorescence:** Evaluates particular indicators of inflammation and skin renewal in histological sections.
- i. **Effects on Immunomodulation:** The measurement of pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines generated during the healing process is known as cytokine profiling.

CONCLUSION:

Each of these evaluation methods provides insights into the performance and effectiveness of exosome-loaded hydrogels for skin regeneration, helping to optimize formulations for clinical applications.

Stem cells (MSCs) are known for their self-renewal activity, extreme development, and multipotent capacity to differentiate into various lines without expressing hematopoietic factors. They can be derived from embryonic tissues with low immunological effects, such as placenta, amniotic fluid, umbilical cord blood, Wharton's jelly, and several tissues in adults such as bone marrow, adipose tissue, dental pulp, thymus, spleen, lung, liver, kidney, brain, and pancreas. MSCs have been confirmed to have an essential role in all wound healing stages, helping to

reduce repair time by improving granulation and re-epithelialization, increasing re-vascularization, regulating inflammation, and managing ECM renovation. However, stem cell therapy alone may not be the best way to heal wounds because using MSCs on the wound micro-environment reduces the activity and lifespan of the transplanted stem cells.

Future studies

Future studies of exosomes loaded on hydrogels for skin regeneration can explore several promising avenues to enhance efficacy and broaden applications. Here are some key areas for inventions

- a. **Research on Mechanisms Comprehending Interactions Between Cells:** Studies can concentrate on the molecular interactions between exosomes and skin cells to clarify how they work to promote tissue regeneration and wound healing.
- b. **Optimizing Formulation Techniques Customized Hydrogel qualities:**
- c. **To enhance exosome loading, release kinetics, and mechanical qualities for particular applications, future research can look at various hydrogel formulations (e.g., composition, crosslinking density).**
- d. **Safety and Long-Term Effectiveness**
- e. **Chronic Wound Models:** Research might evaluate the safety and long-term effects of hydrogels loaded with exosomes in models of chronic wound healing, offering information on the possible uses of these materials in clinical settings. **Stigation.**
- f. **Studies on In Vivo Efficacy**
- g. **Animal Models:** Performing comprehensive in vivo research to assess the therapeutic potential of hydrogels loaded with exosomes in a range of skin regeneration situations, such as burns, diabetic wounds, and surgical scars.
- h. **Synergistic Treatments**
- i. **Multimodal Methods:** examining the potential benefits of mixing exosome-loaded hydrogels with other regenerative medicines (peptides, growth factors, etc.) in order to improve treatment results all around.
- j. **Development of scaffolds and bioprinting**
- k. **3D Bioprinting:** Investigating the use of 3D bioprinting to build intricate structures with hydrogels loaded with exosomes, which may enhance cell viability and facilitate tissue engineering applications.
- l. **Evaluation of Release Profiles Controlled Release Mechanisms:**

- m. Researching exosome release kinetics from hydrogels in various physiological settings in order to enhance therapeutic delivery approaches.
- n. .Clinical Translation and Regulatory Routes
- o. Clinical experiments: Arranging and carrying out clinical experiments to confirm the security and effectiveness of hydrogels loaded with exosomes for skin regeneration in order to get regulatory permission.
- p. Tracking and Imaging Technologies In Vivo Monitoring:
- q. Creating tracking technologies to track exosome distribution, release, and biological consequences in real time within living tissues.
- r. Cross-Field Partnerships
- s. Collaboration A cross Fields: Promoting collaborations across biologists, material scientists, and physicians to advance research and hasten the conversion of discoveries into useful applications.

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